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TECHNOLOGY****EFFECTIVENESS OF PRINCIPLE-CENTERED LEADERSHIP AND
CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SCHOOL HEADS IN LEYTE DIVISION,
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ABSTRACT

The study was conducted to find out the principle-centered leadership of the school heads in Leyte Division, Philippines. Using the descriptive-correlational method, the study used the survey questionnaire as the main data gathering tool.

Most of them were on the age bracket 45 years old and above with a frequency of 67 or 44.7 percent, female got the highest frequency of 126 or 84.0 percent while male respondents got 24 or 16.0, three fourths or 90 percent of the schools had student population of below 1,000, more than one-half or 60 percent of the school heads were master's degree holders, all or 100 percent of the schools managed by the school heads are located in the rural setting, eighty-three or 55.3 percent of the respondents served as school head below 5 years and more than one-third or 78.7 percent opted formal style of passing information.

The principle-centered leadership characteristics manifested by the school heads in terms of regard for learning, self-energy, belief in other people, way of leading life, way of seeing life, exercise or self-renewal and synergy all made in the descriptive category of highly manifested.

The principle-centered leadership manifested by the school heads in terms of staff personnel administration, student personnel administration, financial and physical resources and school community relations were rated highly effective.

As to the relationship of variables, the relationship between the profile of the school heads and their principle-centered leadership characteristics. The computed value for sex is the only one which is lesser than the p-value at alpha 0.05 among other variables in the profile of the school heads. The hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between the profiles of the school head particularly on sex was rejected and therefore significant.

It is further recommended that parallel studies be conducted more specifically on the variables related to gender roles of school heads and their leadership characteristics to generate more data and results to establish greater reliability and validity of the findings threshed out in the study

KEYWORDS: Principle-centered leadership, school heads, Leyte division, Philippines.

INTRODUCTION

Leadership is a complex phenomenon. A great number of definitions have been offered over the years. The literature suggests that there is an important distinction between the two terms: "leader" and "manager". According to Squires (2001), leaders are concerned with the spiritual aspect of their work, that is, they have followers who deeply believe in them and they possess a latent power in organizations.

Stephen Covey in his best-selling book, *Principle-centered Leadership*, discusses that to be successful, effective, and fruitful in any institution, be it at home, business or church, one must operate based on principles. Principles that “are not invented by us or by society, but are the laws of the universe that pertain to human relationships and human organizations. They are part of human condition, consciousness, and conscience.” Principles that will apply “at all times and in all places.”

T. M. Moore advocates that a leader should “begin with the end in mind.” Leadership is not just finishing his own goals, it is also developing others so they can lead, as it is said, “the greatest reward a leader can achieve – the greatest legacy a leader can leave – is a group of talented, self-confident, and cooperative people, who are themselves ready to lead.

Davis (1998) states that two important elements of effective school leadership are establishing a school vision and fostering positive interpersonal relationships. He also acknowledges that developing a school vision takes time and the principal should have the ability to determine the status of the school, identify important aspects of improvement and have a contingency plan to solve problems. In addition to this, they should be knowledgeable about theory and especially those focusing on organizational behavior and leadership. They should possess technical skills needed for managerial responsibilities and the ability to reflect upon their practices in which they skillfully integrate knowledge and skills with experience (Kowalski, 1995).

Organizations and individuals will have to guide their skills, managerial style, systems, and structures in alignment with the interdependent nature of...military alliances, non-governmental organizations. That is, leaders not only value the decentralizing effect of increased information flow upon their own ability to control a situation, they live the reality. Learning new communication skills, manifesting an empowering managerial style, streamlining processes...represent a new approach in achieving mission accomplishment in an effective, optimal fashion. (Rose, 1995).

Strong leadership is the cornerstone of all organizations that are able to achieve and maintain long term success. Few organizations are prepared for the challenge. Nearly any business journal or magazine is likely to include an article on the leadership shortage. Whatever the type of organization--government, education, or business and industry--it seems that effective leadership is in short supply. The problem is likely to escalate as predicted labor shortages increase. Organizations must take pro-active approaches in the development and retention of leadership talent. They must find ways to prepare their current employees for the leadership challenges of the future.

However, managers deal with mundane tasks such as allocation of roles, tasks and resources needed to achieve organizational goals, coordination of the allocated activities and processes and monitoring the everyday operation of the organization. Managers are associated with periods of stability; leaders with periods of turbulence (Bryman, 1993). When people are at peace, happy and satisfied there is hardly any need for leadership. On the other hand, when the human condition is at stake and the situation urges someone to step forward and initiate change, the need for leadership is high (English, 1992). In addition to this, leaders have a vision of the future and they develop strategies that are necessary to bring about changes needed to achieve that vision. However, managers take incremental steps and create timetables to achieve those results (Carlson, 1996).

It proposes that a particular style is appropriate in some situations whereas others are not. However, recent approaches to leadership focus on vision and charisma, a term used by sociologist Max Weber to describe leaders who can lead, but who do not hold “a sanctioned office” (English, 1992). In the late 1970’s the concepts of transactional and transformational leadership emerged.

Bolman and Deal (1991) categorized leadership into four frames: the structural, human resource, political and symbolic frames. Firstly, the structural frame focuses on the importance of formal roles and relationships. The main issue is how to divide the work, and how to assign people to different works and units. Secondly, the human resource frame suggests that organizations are made up of people who have different needs, feelings and interests. The main issue is to make the organization fit its people. Thirdly, the political frame views organizations as political arenas in which resources are scarce and people compete for power. The main issue is to form coalitions and build negotiation.

Lastly, the symbolic frame treats organizations as unique cultures which have rituals, ceremonies, stories, heroes, and myths. The main issue is to focus on meaning, belief, and faith.

Effective leadership begins with the development of a schoolwide vision of commitment to high standards and the success of all students. The principal helps to spell out that vision and get all others on board with it. "The research literature over the last quarter-century has consistently supported the notion that having high expectations for all, including clear and public standards, is one key to closing the achievement gap between advantaged and less advantaged students and for raising the overall achievement of all students," write education leadership researchers at Vanderbilt University (Porter et al., 2008, p. 13).

Since there is just a dearth of studies on how principle-centered leadership is being practiced by the school heads, the researcher would like to propose this study to add to the grayish body of literature. Thus, the conduct of this study becomes novel as it would pave the way to finding out what school heads have to do and how they would shepherd their schools in the context of principle-centered leadership just like in the case of Leyte Division.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Generally, the study aimed to determine the principle-centered leadership of the school heads in Leyte division. Specifically, it would address the following objectives:

1. Find out the school heads' demographic profile in terms of:
 - 1.1 name of school;
 - 1.2 age;
 - 1.3 sex;
 - 1.4 highest educational qualifications;
 - 1.5 number of years as school head;
 - 1.6 location of the school;
 - 1.7 student population of the school;
 - 1.8 style of passing information to the teachers;
2. Determine the principle-centered leadership characteristics manifested by the school heads in terms of:
 - 2.1 Regard for learning;
 - 2.2 Service orientation;
 - 2.3 Self-energy;
 - 2.4 Belief in other people;
 - 2.5 Way of leading life;
 - 2.6 Way of seeing life;
 - 2.7 Synergy and
 - 2.8 Exercise for self-renewal;
3. Assess the principle-centered leadership effectiveness of the school head in terms of:
 - 3.1 Instructional program;
 - 3.2 Staff Personnel Administration;
 - 3.3 Student Personnel Administration;
 - 3.4 Financial and Physical Resource;
 - 3.5 School Community Relations;
4. Ascertain the significant relationship in the following:
 - 4.1 profile of the school heads and the principle-centered leadership characteristics manifested;
 - 4.2 profile of the school heads and principle-centered effectiveness and
 - 4.3 principle-centered leadership characteristics manifested by the school heads and principle-centered effectiveness.

FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

Theoretical framework. The following statements, which are obtained from various intellectuals, provide the theoretical framework of the study.

Central to the theoretical framework of the study is Covey's (1991) Principle-Centered Leadership Theory.

Covey (1991) defines principles as being a combination of values, ideas, norms and teachings that inspire people. He further defines principles as objective and external whereas values are subjective and internal. By using principle centered leadership, Covey (1991) claims that leaders can transform their organisations and their people through communicating vision, clarifying purpose, making behaviour congruent with belief, and aligning procedures with principles, roles and goals. The leader is accepted by followers due to their high moral stance and they achieve a high level of respect. There is little evidence to support Covey's theory and as Jones & Harold (1999) conclude in their research, there is no evidence for accepting Covey's Principle Centered Leadership theory as individual personal characteristics cannot be used as the sole predictor of leadership effectiveness.

Covey emphasizes that principle-centered leadership is practiced from the inside-out. Personal and organizational transformation must come from within. We cannot control what others do, but we can certainly control our own decisions and behaviours. In order to achieve personal and organizational effectiveness, one must also be committed and able to think with a long-term perspective. Covey encourages principle-centered leaders to build greater, more trusting and communicative relationships with others in the workplace and in the home.

As stated above, principle-centered leadership is practiced from the inside out and on four levels. We need to utilize the four principles (security, guidance, wisdom, power) along these four levels (personal, interpersonal, managerial, and organizational).

Throughout the book, Covey has encouraged his readers to change the paradigm with which they view leadership. He acknowledges that there are different leadership paradigms out there (i.e., scientific authoritarian, benevolent authoritarian, human resource), but he believes principle-centered leadership is the leadership paradigm that is most holistic. Principle-centered leadership "embraces the principles of fairness and kindness and makes better use of the talents of people for increased efficiency, but also leads to quantum leaps in personal and organizational effectiveness"

Conceptual framework. The main objective of this study was to determine principle-centered leadership among elementary and secondary school heads in the division of Leyte. The first variable as reflected in the first box is the socio-demographic profile of the elementary and secondary school heads which include: age, sex, civil status, highest educational qualifications, position, number of years as school head, location of school, student population of school and style of passing information to the teachers.

Another variable to be looked into which is contained in the second box is the principle-centered leadership characteristics manifested by the elementary and secondary school heads in terms of regard for learning, service orientation, self-energy, belief in other people, way of leading life, way of seeing life, synergy and exercise for self-renewal.

In like manner, in the third box is the variable which is to assess the principle-centered leadership effectiveness of the school heads in terms of instructional program, staff personnel administration, student personnel administration, financial and physical resource and school community relations which, at the flow of the research process, may be correlated with other variables to find out whether significant relationship exists. The output of the study would be an intervention/scheme plan to improve leadership practices of the school heads in Leyte division. The schematic diagram for the conceptual framework is depicted below.

Figure 1. The conceptual framework of the study

METHODOLOGY

The descriptive-correlational survey method was adopted with the survey questionnaire as the main data gathering tool. This design is appropriate to the study since it only describes various data generated concerning practices of school heads of the principle-centered leadership in the school.

The study was conducted within the elementary and secondary schools in Leyte division.

A total of one hundred fifty (150) elementary and secondary school heads and teachers were purposely chosen as respondents of the study.

The research utilized the survey questionnaire developed through the concepts of Stephen Covey's materials and books on Principle-Centered Leadership. The questionnaire was pre-tested through a dry run in some selected schools not included as respondents of the study.

Part I of the questionnaire includes questions designed to collect demographic information such as age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, student population of the school, location of the school, number of years as school head and style of passing information to the teachers.

Part II is intended to assess the principle-centered characteristics manifested by the school heads on regard for learning, service-orientation, self-energy, belief in other people, way of leading life, way of seeing life, synergy and exercise for self-renewal.

Part III yields information on the principle-centered leadership effectiveness of school heads which covered instructional program, staff personnel administration, student personnel administration, financial and physical resource and school community relations.

Before the full implementation of the study, the researcher prepared letters requesting permission from the Schools Division Superintendent, Elementary and Secondary School Heads and Principals for the formal conduct of the study. Before giving the questionnaire, explanations and detailed instructions were provided to make the participants and respondents feel comfortable and easily comprehend the material. They were given one week to respond, and questionnaires were personally retrieved by the researcher. One hundred percent retrieval of the questionnaires was observed.

The data gathered from questionnaires, interviews and observations was scored as follows.

For principle-centered characteristics manifested by the school head, the following rating scale was used:

Range Weight	Descriptive Category
4.4 - 5.0 5	Very Highly Manifested
3.6 - 4.3 4	Highly Manifested
2.7 - 3.5 3	Manifested
1.8 - 2.6 2	Poorly Manifested
1.0 - 1.7 1	Not Manifested

For principle-centered leadership effectiveness of school head, the following rating scale was used:

Range Weight	Descriptive Category
4.4 - 5.0 5	Very Highly Effective
3.6 - 4.3 4	Highly Effective
2.7 - 3.5 3	Effective
1.8 - 2.6 2	Less Effective
1.0 - 1.7 1	Ineffective

In the analysis and interpretation of data, the following statistical tools were utilized:

To measure the practices of the school heads in principle-centered leadership implementation the simple percentage and the weighted mean were utilized.

The statistical treatment of data in this research included measures of central tendency, measures of variation, testing of hypothesis and linear correlation

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the School Heads

This section illustrates the profile of the school heads in terms of name of school, age, sex, highest educational qualifications: number of years as school head, location of the school, student population of the school, and style of passing information to the teachers. This is shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Profile of the School Heads

Variables	f	%
Age		
60 years old and above (senior citizen)	3	2.0
46-59 years old (old age)	64	42.67
22-45 years old (middle age)	83	55.33
21 years old and below	0	0
Total	150	100
Sex		
Male	24	16.0
Female	126	84.0
Total	150	100
Student Population		
1, 000 above	15	10.0
Below 1, 000	135	90.0
Total	150	100
Highest Educational Qualification		
Doctorate	13	8.7
With Doctoral Units	2	1.3
MA/MAT/MS Graduate	99	60.0
With Masteral Units	19	12.7
Baccalaureate Degree	17	11.3
Total	150	100
Location of School		
Rural	150	100.0
Urban	0	0
Total	150	100
Number of Years as School Head		
15 years and above	1	0.7
5-10 years	66	44.0
Below 5 years	83	55.3
Total	150	100
Style of Passing Information		
Formal	118	78.7
Less Formal	27	18.0
Both	5	3.3
Total	150	100

Age. As shown in the table, most of the respondents' age fell under the age bracket 22-45 years old with a frequency of 83 or 55.33 percent. This means that most of the school heads are middle age and have served for longer period of time.

Sex. As gleaned in the table, female got the highest frequency of 126 or 84.0 percent while male respondents got 24 or 16.0 percent. This just shows that female school heads prevail over their male counterparts.

Student population. As indicated, three fourths or 90 percent of the schools had student population of below 1,000. This data marks that the schools manned by the school heads are not crowded or overpopulated.

Highest educational attainment. More than one-half or 60 percent of the school heads were master's degree holders. Finding declares that the school heads give strong preference on their academic development although there is still bigger room for improvement through increasing the number of their doctorate degree holders.

Location of school. All or 100 percent of the schools managed by the school heads are located in the rural setting.

Number of years as school head. Eighty-three or 55.3 percent of the respondents served as school head below 5 years. This indicates that many of the school heads are novice in their positions.

Style of passing information. More than one-third or 78.7 percent of the respondents opted formal style of passing information.

PRINCIPLE-CENTERED LEADERSHIP CHARACTERISTICS

Manifested by the School Head

The succeeding tables show the principle-centered leadership characteristics manifested by the school heads.

Table 2 Principle-Centered Leadership Characteristics Manifested by the School Head in terms of Regard for Learning

Indicators	WM	Description
1. They are constantly educated by their experiences	3.87	Highly Manifested
2. They read.	3.82	Highly Manifested
3. They seek training.	3.76	Highly Manifested
4. They take classes.	3.81	Highly Manifested
5. They listen to others.	4.04	Highly Manifested
6. They learn through both their eyes and ears.	3.94	Highly Manifested
7. They are curious.	3.90	Highly Manifested
8. They continually expand their competence.	3.96	Highly Manifested
9. They develop new skills , new interests.	3.96	Highly Manifested
10. They discover that the more they know, the more they realize they don't know.	4.01	Highly Manifested
Average weighted mean	3.91	Highly Manifested

As depicted in table 2, the principle-centered leadership characteristics manifested by the school head in terms of regard for learning obtained an average weighted mean of 3.91 interpreted as highly manifested. All of the indicators were found to be on the category of highly manifested. From this prevailing data, it can be inferred that the school heads are open to new learning opportunities. This further implies their passion towards teaching as highly valued profession.

Table 3 Principle-Centered Leadership Characteristics Manifested by the School Head in terms of Service Orientation

Indicators	WM	Description
1. They see life as a mission, not as a career.	3.86	Highly Manifested
2. Their nurturing sources have armed and prepared them for service.	4.06	Highly Manifested
3. Every morning, they yoke up and put on the harness of service, thinking of others.	3.89	Highly Manifested
4. Putting on the harness of service in various stewardships.	3.83	Highly Manifested
5. See themselves allowing someone else to adjust the yoke or harness.	3.73	Highly Manifested

6. See themselves yoked up to another person at their side.	3.79	Highly Manifested
7. Emphasize the principle of service.	3.99	Highly Manifested
8. Believe that effort is important to becoming principle-centered.	3.70	Highly Manifested
9. Attempt to do work as a kind of intellectual or moral exercise.	4.02	Highly Manifested
10. Have a sense of responsibility, service and contribution.	4.10	Highly Manifested
Average weighted mean	3.90	Highly Manifested

As shown in table 3, the principle-centered leadership characteristics manifested by the school head in terms of service orientation garnered an average weighted mean of 3.90 described as highly manifested. This given finding projects the presence of strong service orientation of the school heads and would likely imply that dedication and commitment to do their job is their main thrust.

Table 4 Principle-Centered Leadership Characteristics Manifested by the School Head in terms of Self-Energy

Indicators	WM	Description
1. The countenances of principle-centered people are cheerful, pleasant and happy.	3.95	Highly Manifested
2. Their attitude is optimistic, positive and upbeat.	3.97	Highly Manifested
3. Their spirit is enthusiastic, hopeful and believing.	3.88	Highly Manifested
4. Their positive energy is like an energy field or an aura that surrounds them and that similarly charges or changes weaker, negative energy fields around them.	3.94	Highly Manifested
5. They attract and magnify smaller positive energy fields.	3.75	Highly Manifested
6. When they come into contact with strong, negative energy sources, they tend either to neutralize or to sidestep this negative energy.	3.83	Highly Manifested
7. Sometimes they will leave the negative situation, walking away from its poisonous orbit.	3.69	Highly Manifested
8. Wisdom gives them a sense of how strong it is and a sense of humor and timing in dealing with it.	3.87	Highly Manifested
9. They are aware of the effect of their own energy and understand how they radiate and direct it.	4.03	Highly Manifested
10. In the middle of confusion or contention or negative energy, they strive to be a peacemaker, a harmonizer to undo or reverse destructive energy.	3.85	Highly Manifested
Average weighted mean	3.88	Highly Manifested

Depicted in the table is the principle-centered leadership characteristic manifested by the school heads in terms of self-energy. Under this characteristic, the school heads were rated highly manifested through an average weighted mean of 3.88. Since all indicators fell on the same category, the school heads possessed high self-energy in performing their job. Likewise, it can be implied that the school heads' high self-energy is indicative of their being positive towards work.

Table 5 Principle-Centered Leadership Characteristics Manifested by the School Head in terms of Belief in other People

Indicators	WM	Description
1. Principle-centered people don't overreact to negative behaviors, criticism, or human weaknesses.	3.84	Highly Manifested
2. They don't feel built up when they discover the weaknesses of others.	3.67	Highly Manifested
3. They are not naïve. They are aware of weakness. They realize that behavior and potential are two different things.	3.85	Highly Manifested
4. They believe in the unseen potential of all people.	3.91	Highly Manifested
5. They feel grateful for their blessings and feel naturally to compassionately forgive and forget the offenses of others.	4.05	Highly Manifested
6. They don't carry grudges.	3.89	Highly Manifested
7. They refuse to label other people, to stereotype, categorize and prejudice.	3.97	Highly Manifested
8. They see the oak tree in the acorn and understand the process of helping the acorn become a great oak.	3.95	Highly Manifested
9. They consider creating a climate for growth and opportunity.	3.92	Highly Manifested
10. They don't believe that the key lies in them, in their techniques, in doing "their thing" to others.	3.85	Highly Manifested
Average weighted mean	3.89	Highly Manifested

Presented in table 5 is the principle-centered leadership characteristic manifested by the school heads in terms of belief in other people which garnered an average weighted mean of 3.89 labeled as highly manifested. This finding points to the good character and pleasant relationship exhibited by the school heads towards other people. Such also yields an implication that school heads build a way for other people to be recognized and treated well

Table 6 Principle-Centered Leadership Characteristics Manifested by the School Head in terms of Way of Leading Life

Indicators	WM	Description
1. They read the best literature and magazines and keep up with current affairs and events.	3.90	Highly Manifested
2. They are active socially, having many friends and a few confidants.	3.96	Highly Manifested
3. They are active intellectually, having many interests.	3.93	Highly Manifested
4. They read, watch, observe and learn.	4.11	Highly Manifested
5. Within the limits of age and health, they are active physically.	3.98	Highly Manifested
6. They have a healthy sense of humor, particularly laughing at themselves and not at others' expense.	3.91	Highly Manifested
7. They can feel their own worth, which is manifest by their courage and integrity and by the absence of a need to brag, to drop names and to borrow strength from possessions or credentials or titles or past achievements.	4.07	Highly Manifested

8. They are open in their communication, simple, direct and nonmanipulative.	3.98	Highly Manifested
9. They are not extremists.	3.86	Highly Manifested
10. Their actions and attitudes are proportionate to the situation-balance, temperate, moderate and wise.	3.89	Highly Manifested
Average weighted mean	3.96	Highly Manifested

As seen on the table, the principle-centered leadership characteristic manifested by the school heads in terms of way of leading life posted an average weighted mean of 3.96 touted as highly manifested. Such information proposes positive way of leading life as exuded by the school heads. In like manner, this implies that the school heads view life in a meaningful way and they are always upbeat in all ways.

Table 7 Principle-Centered Leadership Characteristics Manifested by the School Head in terms of Way of Seeing Life

Indicators	WM	Description
1. Principle-centered people savor life.	3.85	Highly Manifested
2. They have no need to categorize and stereotype everything and everybody in life to give them a sense of certainty and predictability.	3.74	Highly Manifested
3. They see old faces freshly, old scenes as if for the first time.	3.81	Highly Manifested
4. They are like courageous explorers going on an expedition into uncharted territories.	3.87	Highly Manifested
5. They are really not sure what is going to happen, but they are confident it will be exciting and growth producing.	3.81	Highly Manifested
6. Their security lies in their initiative, resourcefulness, creativity, willpower, courage, stamina and native intelligence.	4.06	Highly Manifested
7. They rediscover people each time they meet them.	3.81	Highly Manifested
8. They ask questions and get involved.	3.89	Highly Manifested
9. They are completely present when they listen.	3.79	Highly Manifested
10. They resist becoming any person's disciple.	3.77	Highly Manifested
Average weighted mean	3.84	Highly Manifested

From the table, it can be viewed that the principle-centered leadership characteristic of the school head in terms of way of seeing life attained an average weighted mean of 3.84 considered highly manifested. This finding shows the ways and manners of seeing life by the school heads. The idea suggests that the school heads positive way of looking at life is also tantamount to how it translates their views of seeing themselves in the job.

Table 8 Principle-Centered Leadership Characteristics Manifested by the School Head in terms of Synergy

Indicators	WM	Description
1. Principle-centered people are synergistic.	3.89	Highly Manifested
2. They are change catalysts.	3.95	Highly Manifested

3. They improve almost any situation they get into.	3.89	Highly Manifested
4. They work as smart as they work hard.	3.79	Highly Manifested
5. They are amazingly productive, but in new and creative ways.	3.71	Highly Manifested
6. In team endeavors, they build on their strengths and strive to complement their weaknesses with the strengths of others.	3.87	Highly Manifested
7. Delegation for results is easy and natural to them, since they believe in others' strengths and capacities.	4.12	Highly Manifested
8. Since they are not threatened by the fact that others are better in some ways, they feel no need to supervise them closely.	3.97	Highly Manifested
9. They learn to separate the people from the problem.	3.87	Highly Manifested
10. They focus on other person's interests and concerns rather than fight over positions.	3.83	Highly Manifested
Average weighted mean	3.89	Highly Manifested

For table 8, it is portrayed that the principle-centered leadership characteristic manifested by the school heads in terms of synergy achieved an average weighted mean of 3.89 equivalent to highly manifested. Such rating represents the high synergy of the school heads which, as implied, is reflective of valuing others and getting to be with them pleasantly.

Table 9 Principle-Centered Leadership Characteristics Manifested by the School Head in terms of Exercise for Self-Renewal

Indicators	WM	Description
1. They regularly exercise the four dimensions of the human personality: physical, mental, emotional and spiritual	3.84	Highly Manifested
2. They participate in some kind of balanced, moderate, regular program of aerobic exercise.	3.88	Highly Manifested
3. They exercise their minds through reading, creative problem solving, writing and visualizing.	3.84	Highly Manifested
4. Emotionally they make an effort to be patient, to listen to others with genuine empathy.	3.86	Highly Manifested
5. Spiritually they focus on prayer, scripture study, meditation and fasting.	3.88	Highly Manifested
6. They show unconditional love.	3.95	Highly Manifested
7. They accept responsibility for their own lives.	3.95	Highly Manifested
8. They take responsibility of their decisions and actions.	3.91	Highly Manifested
9. They try to improve the quality, productivity and satisfaction of their every other hour of the day.	3.85	Highly Manifested
10. They value that soon experience will impact the good on their life.	3.97	Highly Manifested
Average weighted mean	3.89	Highly Manifested

Portrayed in table 9 is the principle-centered leadership manifested by the school heads in terms of exercise for self-renewal which brought an average weighted mean of 3.89 and described as highly manifested. As shown, the school heads led a balanced life physically, emotionally, intellectually and spiritually. This would also imply that they are always up on something good for themselves and their fellows.

Table 10 Principle-Centered Leadership Effectiveness of the School Head In terms of Instructional Program

Indicators	WM	Description
Offering assistance to teachers in the location of teaching materials.	3.99	Highly Effective
Helping teachers to develop new instructional materials.	3.95	Highly Effective
Offering assistance to teachers in the selection of textbooks for students.	3.95	Highly Effective
Coordinating the general instructional activities of teachers	4.10	Highly Effective
Coordinating the presentation of social programs for slow learners	3.99	Highly Effective
Average weighted mean	4.00	Highly Effective

As disclosed in table 10, the principle-centered leadership effectiveness of the school heads in terms of instructional program was rated an average weighted mean of 4.00 described as highly effective. All of the indicators fell on the category highly effective. The results would imply that the school heads perform very effectively when it comes to instructional program.

Table 11 Principle-Centered Leadership Effectiveness of the School Head In terms of Staff Personnel Administration

Indicators	WM	Description
Ensuring that teacher understand their limit to independent action.	3.94	Highly Effective
Accepting responsibility for the work he/she delegates to staff.	4.06	Highly Effective
Allowing teachers a measure of authority in doing their duties.	4.01	Highly Effective
Viewing teacher's attendance to class as very important	4.06	Highly Effective
Checking who does his/her work.	4.12	Highly Effective
Assisting staff on personal problems.	4.04	Highly Effective
Recruiting staff.	3.92	Highly Effective
Average weighted mean	4.02	Highly Effective

Table 11 specifies the principle-centered leadership manifested by the school heads in terms of staff personnel administration which generated an average weighted mean of 4.02 interpreted as highly effective. The data marks the way the school heads relate to their staff personnel which implies their being good-natured and trustworthy.

Table 12 Principle-Centered Leadership Effectiveness of the School Head In terms of Student Personnel Administration

Indicators	WM	Description
Helping teachers to monitor student's progress through examinations	3.95	Highly Effective
Discussing with student regularly concerning their welfare	3.82	Highly Effective
Making himself/herself available for student consultation	3.96	Highly Effective
Ensuring that students who come late are disciplined	3.89	Highly Effective
Ensuring the orientation of new students in his/her school	4.06	Highly Effective
Showing concern on school performance in examinations	4.00	Highly Effective
Average weighted mean	3.95	Highly Effective

It can be gleaned from table 12 that the principle-centered leadership characteristic manifested by the school heads in terms of student personnel administration obtained an average weighted mean of 3.95 known to be highly effective. This would mean that the school heads maintain a good and positive relationship with their student personnel. Further, this also implies that the school heads are proactive about advancing students' welfare.

Table 13 Principle-Centered Leadership Effectiveness of the School Head In terms of Financial and Physical Resource

Indicators	WM	Description
Evaluating the use of physical resources in his/her school	3.97	Highly Effective
Evaluating the use of financial resources in his/her schools	4.01	Highly Effective
Obtaining revenue from appropriate quarters for his/her school	3.94	Highly Effective
Coordinating money spending to avoid unnecessary expenses	3.97	Highly Effective
Making budget estimates for his/her school	4.03	Highly Effective
Providing immediate replacements to damaged classroom equipment	3.93	Highly Effective
Average weighted mean	3.97	Highly Effective

Table 13 views the principle-centered leadership characteristic manifested by the school heads in terms of financial and physical resources which posed an average weighted mean of 3.97 under descriptive category of highly effective. Clearly, evidence from this finding establishes sound claim of the school heads ability and skill in managing financial and physical resources of the school.

Table 14 Principle-Centered Leadership Effectiveness of the School Head In terms of School Community Relations

Indicators	WM	Description
Ensuring good rapport on school community relations	4.05	Highly Effective
Planning meetings for good relations	4.07	Highly Effective
Understanding of the values of the society in which his/her school operates	3.99	Highly Effective
Listening to advice from members of the society	4.05	Highly Effective
Ensuring regular evaluation of school community relations of his/her school	4.03	Highly Effective
Involving the community on school projects	4.01	Highly Effective
Average weighted mean	4.04	Highly Effective

From table 14, it can be noted that the principle-centered leadership effectiveness of the school heads in terms of school community relations rolled out an average weighted mean of 4.04 and considered highly effective. From the given data, it can be implied that there is harmonious linkage between the school and the community.

Relationship of Variables

This section presents the relationship of variables: the profile of the school head and the principle-centered leadership characteristics manifested, profile and effectiveness manifested by the school head and principle-centered leadership and effectiveness manifested by the school head. These are presented in Tables 14, 15 and 16.

Table 15 Significant Relationship Between the Profile of the School Head and the Principle-Centered Leadership Characteristics

Variables	df	Chi-Square Value	Asymp. Sig.	Interpretation
Age	117	138.792	.083	Not significant
Sex	39	56.006	.038*	Significant
Student population	39	44.166	.262	Not significant
Highest Educational Qualification	156	125.392	.137	Not significant
Number of Years				
Style of Passing Information	39	34.747	.664	Not significant
	78	97.793	.064	Not significant

*Significant at 0.05

** Significant at 0.01

As shown in the table, it could be seen that the results indicate the relationship between the profile of the school heads and their principle-centered leadership characteristics. The computed value for sex is the only one which is lesser than the p-value at alpha 0.05 among other variables in the profile of the school heads. The hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between the profiles of the school head particularly on sex was rejected and therefore significant. This would imply that there exists a difference between male and female school heads in terms of their leadership characteristics.

As to the sex factor of the school heads, it can be seen from the table that, for the male, the biggest number with a frequency of 13 or 54.17 percent and the lowest was with a frequency of 3 or 12.5 percent known as very highly manifested. For the female, they got the highest number with a frequency of 98 or 77.78 percent while the lowest was

with a frequency of 7 or 5.57 percent. The results evidently indicate that there is a greater number of female school heads who highly manifested principle-centered leadership characteristics as compared to the male.

Table 16 Significant Relationship Between the Profile and Effectiveness Manifested by the School Head

Variables	df	Chi-Square Value	Asymp. Sig.	Interpretation
Age	51	44.236	.737	Not significant
Sex	17	8.365	.958	Not Significant
Student population	17	7.234	.876	Not significant
Highest Educational Qualification	68	62.596	.629	Not significant
Number of Years				
Style of Passing Information	17	17.104	.447	Not significant
	17	25.833	.078	Not significant

*Significant at 0.05

** Significant at 0.01

It can be figured out in the table that, on the relationship between the profile of the school heads and their effectiveness manifested, on variables age, sex, student population, highest educational qualification, number of years as school head and style of passing information and the effectiveness manifested by them, the p-value were greater than the asym. sig. values at alpha =.05. The hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between the profiles of the school and the effectiveness manifested by them was rejected and therefore not significant. This would imply that the profile of the school heads are not relate or does not affect the effectiveness manifested by them in school.

Table 17 Significant Relationship between the Principle-Centered Leadership Characteristics and Effectiveness Manifested by the School Head

Variables	r	P-value	Interpretation
Principle-Centered Leadership Characteristics and Effectiveness Manifested by the School Head	.094	.622	Not Significant Ho Accepted

*Significant at 0.05

** Significant at 0.01

The table shows that the computed r (.094) and P-value are greater than the significant level at 0.05. The hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between the principle-centered leadership characteristics and effectiveness manifested by the school heads was accepted and therefore not significant. This manifests an implication that the principle-centered leadership characteristics of the school heads do not eventually affect their effectiveness.

CONCLUSION

After thorough analysis of the results based from the findings gathered in the study, the researcher formed her conclusions. The school heads in Leyte division have exhibited and practiced principle-centered leadership in their respective work stations. They are ideal leaders who embody high manifestation of regard for learning, self-energy, belief in other people, way of leading life, way of seeing life, exercise or self-renewal and synergy; and also they are very effective in terms of staff personnel administration, student personnel administration, financial and physical resources and school community relations.

On the other hand, female and male school heads have shown differences with the ways they conceived and put into practice principle-centered leadership.

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